

INFLUENCE OF NON-ELECTROLYTES ON THE CATHODE EFFICIENCY OF COPPER DEPOSITION.

BY SHRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI, DUSEHYANT NARASINGASA SOLANKI
AND T. V. SUBBA RAO.

A quantitative study has been made of the deposition of copper from acidified copper sulphate solution in the presence of varying concentrations of the non-electrolytes : ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, glycerol and acetone. The increase of the cathode efficiency with the concentration of the non-electrolyte up to the limiting value has been attributed to the decreasing solvent action of the bath solution over the deposited copper. Evidence has also been adduced for the possible existence of the complex cation between the metallic copper ion and the non-electrolyte. The depression in the cathode efficiency, especially in the presence of large excess of acetone and methyl alcohol, has been attributed to an interaction between the medium and the conducting material.

The influence of addition agents on the electrolysis of aqueous copper sulphate has been observed in the electrolytic extraction and refinement of copper. The addition of free sulphuric acid was found to be essential to get satisfactory and concordant results with the deposition of copper as has been pointed out by Campbell and Dickson (*Proc. Phil. Soc. Glasgow*, 1900, 31, 52), Ellwood and Spear (*Eighth Inter. Cong. Appl. Chem.*, 1912, 21, 99) and others. Ellwood and Spear, from the study of the effects of inorganic addition agents in general, suggested that the function of such agents is to keep the copper in solution ; moreover, the addition of these inorganic materials increases the conductivity of the electrolyte, which has got its own advantages as well as disadvantages. Emil Bose (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1902, 26, 47), Gannon (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1894, A 55, 66), Gray (*Phil. Mag.*, 1888, v, 26, 183) and others studied the applicability of Faraday's law and concluded that slight deviations of the law were apparent, the departures being attributed to several disturbing factors, *viz.*,

(a) The existence of the cation in two forms, leading to a possible disturbing factor, due to the reaction, $M + M \dots \dots 2M$.

(b) Dissolution of the deposited copper due to a solvent action of the solution.

(c) Chemical corrosion brought about by dissolved oxygen. A bibliography of many of the investigations upon the deposition of copper in the

presence of gelatin and similar addition agents in general, will be found in an excellent paper of Frolich (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1924, **40**, 67). Since then the important papers of Fuseya and co-workers (Fuseya and Murata, *ibid.*, 1926, **50**, 235; Fuseya and Nagano, *ibid.*, 1927, **52**, 249) and of Marie and Buffat (*J. chim. phys.*, 1927, **24**, 470), and Marie and Claudel (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, **187**, 170) have been published.

The possible rôle of these addition agents in general, has been investigated in a review by Blum (*Colloid Symposium Monograph*, 1921, **V**, 300) who suggests the following factors for cases in which the addition agent has actually been found in the cathode deposits: "(1) Co discharge of colloid particles and metal ions, (2) discharge of complex ions containing the metal and the colloid, (3) adsorption of colloid upon the face of the metal deposit, or (4) mechanical inclusion in the deposit." Blum further states in regard to these various possibilities that "it is difficult from the meagre data available to suggest the relative probabilities of these processes.....". However, other workers have expressed preference for one or the other of the particular views outlined above. Thus Bancroft (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1913, **23**, 266) tacitly assumes that adsorption accounts for the inclusion of the addition agent in the deposit; Fuseya and Murata (*loc. cit.*) postulated the existence of complex cations formed from the metal ion and addition agent and produce evidence to show that such complex ions are doubtless formed. The results of Marie and Buffat (*loc. cit.*) were further confirmed, recently, by Taft and Messmore (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 2585) who came to the conclusion that the deposited copper adsorbs gelatin on its surface and have established that complex ions are formed between Cu^{++} and gelatin and that electrochemical process occurring at the cathode is primarily a discharge of Cu^{++} . Datta and Dhar (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 1156), from the comparison of the copper coulometers containing varying quantities of cane sugar and of tartaric acid with silver coulometers, came to the conclusion that the mass of the deposit increases to a limiting value with the increasing content of the addition agent and is by no means restricted to the case of gelatin. Foerster and Siedel (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, **14**, 106) reported that in the electrolysis of copper sulphate solution, addition of alcohol gave more concordant results. These experiments however, were not carried out on a quantitative basis and it is not clear as to how the addition of alcohols and other non-electrolytes affects the the conditions of the bath. The authors, however, have supposed that "the alcohol decreases the concentration of the copper ions and therefore the solubility of the deposited copper in copper sulphate solution."

Richard, Collins and Heimrod (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **32**, 321) considering the various factors which led to the deficits in the deposit, in agreement with the views of Foerster and Siedel (*loc. cit.*), suggested that the mean value of the atomic weight of copper should be 63.563, which is less than the value 63.604 obtained by purely chemical means.

The following experiments were carried out to investigate the apparent discrepancies in the cathodic copper deposits from those to be anticipated from Faraday's law and if possible to throw light on the influence of some non-electrolytes in improving the quality and the amount of deposit.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The chemicals employed $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, H_2SO_4 , etc. were Merck's guaranteed reagents. Ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and acetone were freshly distilled before use. Pure glycerine was used. As it has already been shown by Gannon (*loc. cit.*), Campbell and Dickson (*loc. cit.*), Ellwood and Spear (*loc. cit.*) and others that free sulphuric acid is beneficial, so a solution of the following composition as recommended by Oettel (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, **17**, 543) was prepared.

Copper sulphate crystals = 150 g.

Concentrated sulphuric acid ($d = 1.84$) = 50 g.

Diluted to one litre with distilled water.

In the following experiments 175 c.c. of the same stock solution, diluted to 200 c.c. with the requisite amount of non-electrolyte and water, was used as the bath solution. The copper cathode ($5 \times 2 \times 0.2$ cm.) used was given an initial thick and uniform deposit of copper. A steady current of 50 milliamps. obtained by using storage batteries (4.3 volts) and adjustable resistance was allowed to pass through the bath solution for a known interval of time, usually 1 hour. A precision milliammeter of Weston's model was used to read the current. The cathode at the end of the experiment was washed free from the electrolyte with distilled water thoroughly, then with rectified spirit to remove water and finally with ether to remove traces of alcohol. It was then thoroughly dried over the fan, allowed to cool and weighed. Each observation was repeated at least twice. These are recorded in Tables I-IV.

In Table I. vertical column 1 gives the concentration of alcohol added, expressed as a percentage by volume; columns 2 and 3 give respectively the weight of cathode before and after deposition; column 4 gives the weight of copper deposited; column 5 gives the theoretical or calculated

value for the deposit of copper in accordance with Faraday's law ; column 6 gives the time in hours ; column 7 gives the cathode efficiency *viz.*, the ratio of the weight of copper deposited (column 4) to the weight of copper calculated (column 5), expressed as a percentage. The results in Tables II-IV are recorded similarly.

TABLE I.

Electrolyte = Acidified $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} = 13.13\%$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 4.4\%$. Non-electrolyte = Ethyl alcohol. Temp. = $24 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Current = 50 m. amps.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
% EtOH.	Wt. of cathode Initial. Final.		Wt. of copper Deposited. Calc.		Duration.	Cathode efficiency.
0 c.c.	31.7980 g.	31.8553 g.	0.0573 g.	0.0593 g.	1 hr.	96.63
"	31.9132	31.9705	0.0573	"	1	96.63
0.3	32.1142	32.1722	0.0580	"	1	97.81
"	32.1720	32.2300	0.0580	"	1	97.81
0.5	32.3458	32.4042	0.0584	"	1	98.47
"	32.4621	32.5207	0.0586	"	1	98.81
"	32.5207	32.5790	0.0583	"	1	98.31
1.0	32.5791	32.6376	0.0585	"	1	98.65
"	32.9891	33.0477	0.0586	"	1	98.81
2.0	33.3595	33.4184	0.0589	"	1	99.31
"	33.4184	33.4768	0.0584	"	1	98.47
"	33.4768	33.5354	0.0586	"	1	98.81
5.0	33.6520	33.7106	0.0586	"	1	98.81
"	34.0603	34.1191	0.0588	"	1	99.14

TABLE II.

Electrolyte = Acidified $\text{CuSO}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O} = 13.13\%$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 4.4\%$.
 Non-electrolyte = Methyl alcohol. Temp. = $24 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Current = 50 m. amps.

1 % MeOH.	2 Wt. of cathode Initial.	3 Final.	4 Wt. of copper Deposited.	5 Calc.	6 Duration.	7 Cathode efficiency.
0 c.c.	34.1343 g.	34.1916 g.	0.0573 g.	0.0593 g	1 hr.	96.63
"	34.1916	34.2489	0.0573	"	"	96.63
1.0	34.3664	34.4245	0.0581	"	"	97.97
"	34.4245	34.4826	0.0581	"	"	97.97
5.0	34.5406	34.5993	0.0587	"	"	98.97
"	34.5993	34.6578	0.0585	"	"	98.65
10.0	34.6578	34.7161	0.0583	"	"	
"	34.7161	34.7744	0.0583	"	"	98.31
"	34.7746	34.8331	0.0585	"	"	98.65
"	34.8909	34.9493	0.0584	"	"	98.47
*20.0	34.9493	35.0069	0.0576	"	"	97.12
"	35.0070	35.0650	0.0580	"	"	97.81

* In this case crystallisation of copper compound begins.

TABLE III.

Electrolyte = Acidified $\text{CuSO}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O} = 13.13\%$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 4.4\%$.
 Non-electrolyte = Acetone. Temp. = $24 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Current = 50 m. amps.

1 % Acetone.	2 Wt. of cathode Initial.	3 Final.	4 Wt. of copper Deposited.	5 Calc.	6 Duration.	7 Cathode efficiency.
0 c.c.	34.1343 g.	34.1916 g.	0.0573 g.	0.0593 g.	1 hr.	96.63
"	34.1916	34.2489	0.0573	"	"	96.63
1.0	35.2180	35.3055	0.0875	0.0890	1.5	98.31
"	35.3054	35.3637	0.0583	0.0593	1	98.31
5.0	35.3637	35.4219	0.0582	0.0593	"	98.13
"	35.5378	35.5959	0.0581	0.0593	"	97.97
"	33.6544	35.7126	0.0582	"	"	98.13
10.0	35.9143	35.9726	0.0583	"	"	98.31
"	35.9726	36.0309	0.0583	"	"	98.31
* 20.0	36.0310	36.0889	0.0579	"	"	97.63
"	36.0889	36.1468	0.0579	"	"	97.63

* In this case also separation of crystalline copper compound takes place.

TABLE IV.

Electrolyte = Acidified $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O} = 13.13\%$; $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 4.4\%$. Non-electrolyte = Glycerine. Temp. = $24 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Current = 50 m. amps.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
% Glycerine.	Wt. of cathode Initial.	Final.	Wt. of copper Deposited.	Copper Calc.	Duration.	Cathode efficiency.
0 c.c.	34.1343 g.	34.1916 g.	0.0573 g.	0.0593 g.	1 hr.	96.63
"	34.1916	34.2489	0.0573	"	"	96.63
1.0	36.2044	36.2628	0.0584	"	"	98.47
"	36.2628	36.3212	0.0584	"	"	98.47
5.0	36.3794	36.4382	0.0588	"	"	99.15
"	36.4380	36.4966	0.0586	"	"	98.81
"	36.4966	36.6142	0.1176	0.1186	2	99.15
10.0	36.6726	36.7315	0.0589	0.0593	1	99.31
"	36.7311	36.7899	0.0588	"	"	99.15
20.0	36.8484	36.9073	0.0589	"	"	99.31
"	36.9073	36.9661	0.0588	"	"	99.15

Curves in Fig. 1 show the variation of the cathode efficiency as a function of the percentage of ethyl alcohol and acetone; curves in Fig. 2 refer, to the use of glycerine and methyl alcohol.

DISCUSSION.

Our data (*cf.* Tables I-IV) on the quantitative study of the deposition of copper from acidified copper sulphate solution in the presence of the varying concentrations of the non-electrolytes: ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, glycerine and acetone show that the cathode efficiency (*cf.* column 7, Tables I-IV) of copper increases steadily with the progressive addition of the non-electrolyte, in all cases, till it approaches a limiting value; it remains constant, being unaffected with further addition, in the case of glycerine (*cf.* Table IV, Fig. 2) but is depressed in the case of methyl alcohol (*cf.* Table II, Fig. 2) and acetone (*cf.* Table III, Fig. 1). The effect of the non-electrolytes studied, on the limiting value for the cathode efficiency is in the descending order: glycerine > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > acetone, the limiting value being greatest in the presence of glycerine and least in the presence of acetone.

The apparent deficit in the copper deposit during the electrolysis of acidified copper sulphate solution, in absence of the non-electrolytes, can be attributed to solvent action on the deposited copper in the bath solution; that the loss thus brought about, is a function of temperature and electrode

area of the cathode surface, is demonstrated by the work of Gray (*loc. cit.*), Foerster and Siedel (*loc. cit.*) and Richard, Collins and Heimrod (*loc. cit.*). Emil Bose (*loc. cit.*) attributed deviations from Faraday's law, when using salts, the cations of which can exist in two forms, to a possible disturbing factor, due to the reaction, $M + M \dots \dots 2M$ Gannon (*loc. cit.*) has observed that copper sulphate in solution does not conform rigorously to the simple form, in which Faraday's law is generally expressed. The discharge of hydrogen, due to high current density is also another disturbing factor which gives too low a deposit. The addition of non-electrolytes, however, alters the condition of the bath and brings about the diminution in the concentration of the copper ions in the solution, thus lowering the solvent effect. It is, therefore, to be anticipated that an increase in the cathode efficiency would come about by increasing the concentration of the non-electrolyte up to a certain limiting value; our foregoing results (*cf.* curves in Figs. 1-2) are in agreement with this deduction (*cf.* also Foerster and Siedel, *loc. cit.*).

FIG. 1.

In connection with the limiting value for the cathode efficiency, it is interesting to point out that with ethyl alcohol the efficiency steadily increases with the alcohol content up to 5%, and shows tendency towards the limiting value, which is not actually attained within the concentration range studied, unlike with the rest of the non-electrolytes, in which cases the limiting value is actually attained. The concentrations of the non-electrolytes corresponding to the limiting value for cathode efficiency are

FIG. 2.

found to be in simple molecular ratio with the molecular concentration of copper sulphate. The occurrence of maxima on the curves corresponding to the limiting value, may, possibly be attributed to the formation of a complex cation of the type $[Cu, n(CH_3OH)]^{++}$, $[Cu, n(\text{glycerine})]^{++}$, etc. Such a possibility for the metallic copper ion to form a complex cation with the addi-

tion agent in general, has been shown, beyond doubt, to be valid in several cases as shown by several investigators: Fuseya and Murata (*loc. cit.*) in presence of addition agents in general; Fuseya and Nagano (*loc. cit.*) in the presence of glycocoil; Taft and Malm (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 874) in the presence of gum arabic; Taft and Messmore (*loc. cit.*) in the presence of gelatin, further confirmed from transport number measurements by Mutscheller (*Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1915, 13, 353).

In spite of a general similarity of the behaviour shown by acetone it must be emphasised that acetone stands apart from the rest of the non-electrolytes investigated, *i.e.*, it does not contain (OH) hydroxyl group, so characteristic of the rest of the non-electrolytes employed. Capacity for forming a complex ion with copper is well known to depend, not only upon the colloidal nature of the addition agent, but also upon whether or not it contains hydroxyl or amino groups. The presence of a ketonic group is, therefore, anticipated to reduce this possibility, as is illustrated by the fact that addition of acetone raises the cathode efficiency to the least extent. Glycerine, probably due to its semi-colloidal and polyhydroxylic nature,

seems to be the most efficient in its action amongst the non-electrolytes studied. The limiting value in the descending order, glycerine > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > acetone, might be attributed to a gradually diminishing tendency for complex formation as we pass from glycerine to acetone. Further evidence for a possible complex formation between the metal ion and the non-electrolyte has been adduced from the work carried out in these laboratories by Joshi and Padmanabhan (*This issue*, p. 176), the complex formation being suggested by inflexions on curves obtained by plotting transport number, viscosity, cathode efficiency, refractive index and conductivity against increasing concentrations of the non-electrolyte present in the system.

Our data with acetone and methyl alcohol show that cathode efficiency, after reaching the maximum, is reduced with further addition. This might be due to an interaction between the conducting material and the medium. In the presence of large excess of these non-electrolytes, due to limited solubility of the electrolyte in the medium, it is possible to imagine a stage of supersaturation, or even actual separation of the salt, a stage which was actually realised, especially in the presence of 20% non-electrolyte, as mentioned in the foot notes, in Tables II and III. The separation of the salt naturally alters the concentration and thus upsets the conditions of the bath and this might be one of the possible factors responsible for the observed depression in the cathode efficiency.

ELECTROCHEMISTRY SECTION,
CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY,
BENARES.

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